

Relativistic Corrections to the 1D Nonrelativistic Case for the Hulthen Potential

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In (1) an exact solution to the Klein Gordon equation with a scalar Hulthen potential $V(x) = S \exp(-ax) / (1 - q \exp(-a))$ is obtained using the Nikiforov-Uvarov method. From the results, one may see that energy E goes as $m + B(a,q)m + C(a,q) + O(1/m)$ etc. Often the second order term of E is of the order of $1/m$, but such is not the case here. Nevertheless, if $B(a,q)$ is small, one may still obtain the usual nonrelativistic relations. In this note, we examine the ground state for which a solution to the Klein Gordon equation may be found by inspection. We then consider the equations needed to compute various orders of the full energy solution in order to find nonrelativistic results. We find the $B(a,q)m$ term is obtained from: $2m V(x) W(x) = -\sqrt{e^*e + 2e^*m} d/dx W(x)$. This is not the Schrodinger equation, but we show that the kinetic energy $-1/2m d/dx d/dx W(x)$ associated with the wavefunction $W(x)$ of this equation yields the nonrelativistic result, plus a term which can be dropped. For levels above the ground state, we show that $2m V(x) W(x) = -\sqrt{e^*e + 2e^*m} d/dx W(x)$ may be solved by the Nikiforov-Uvarov method. This seems to suggest that in the nonrelativistic case, it may be easier to solve an equation slightly different from the Schrodinger equation, but compatible with the relativistic equation.

We also examine a second correction to the energy.

Nikiforov-Uvarov Solution

The Nikiforov-Uvarov method allows one to find Rodrigues polynomial solutions (multiplied by a function) (linked to a hypergeometric DE) for the case of certain second order DEs. Usually a transformation is involved. In (1) and (2), the following Klein Gordon equation is solved in detail for:

$$V(x) = S \exp(-ax) / (1 - q \exp(-ax)) \quad ((1))$$

For simplicity, we set $S=1$ in this note.

{ To bring in S , one may scale:

$$\{ (E/S)^*(E/S) - (m/S + V/S)^2 \} W(x) = -d/d (Sx) d/d (xS) W(x) \quad \}$$

With $S=1$, the Klein-Gordon equation is:

$$(E^*E - m^*m - V(x)^*V(x) - 2mV(x)) W(x) = -d/dx d/dx W(x) \quad ((2))$$

The solution for E is given as:

$$E(q,a,S) = +/- 1/(4q kn) \sqrt{\{ (kn^2 - 4S^2)[(2S + 4qm)^2 - kn^2] \}}$$

where $kn = \sqrt{q^2 a^2 + 4S^2} + qa(2n+1)$

Consider $S=1$ and $n=0$ (the ground state.) Then:

$$E = \pm \frac{1}{4qkn} \sqrt{(kn^2 - 4^2)[4 + 16qm + 16q2m^2 - kn^2]} \quad ((2a))$$

One may perform a power series expansion for E in powers of m or $1/m$ etc.

In the next section, we consider explicitly a ground state solution and carry out the power series expansion explicitly.

If one considers m^*m as the leading term in ((2a)) then:

$$E = e + m = m(1 - 4/(kn^*kn)) \text{ to this leading order with } kn = qa^2(n+1) \text{ if } aq \gg 1.$$

Ground State Solution

It is possible to find a ground state solution to ((2)) by inspection. One first writes:

$$W(x) = \exp(-\sqrt{-E^*E + m^*m}x) G(x) \quad ((3)) \text{ Then:}$$

$$-V(x)V(x)G - 2mV(x)G = -2\sqrt{-E^*E + m^*m} \frac{d}{dx}G - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}G \quad ((4))$$

Note $E < m$ for bound states as stated in (1).

One may note that for $G = (1 - q \exp(-ax))^b$, $\frac{d}{dx}G = baqG$ and

$$\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}G = -ba^*a q VG + ba^*aq^*q (b-1) V^*V G$$

$$\text{Thus: } W(x) = \exp[-\sqrt{-E^*E + m^*m}x] (1 - q \exp(-ax))^b \quad ((5))$$

One now has to solve for b and E :

$$-2m = ba^*aq - 2baq \sqrt{-E^*E + m^*m} \text{ and } -1 = -a^*a q^*q b(b-1)$$

$$\text{Thus: } b = .5 \pm \sqrt{.25 + 1/q^2 a^2} \quad ((6)) \text{ and}$$

$$E^*E = \left\{ -\frac{m}{(bqa)} + \frac{ba}{2} \right\}^2 + m^*m \quad ((7))$$

If one writes $E = e + m$, then e is of the order of m , but its coefficient may be a small number, to allow for a nonrelativistic term.

$$E = \sqrt{m^*m \left[-1/(baq)^2 + 1 \right] - mb/q - (ba)^2/4} \quad ((8))$$

This may be expanded:

$$E = m \sqrt{C_1 - b/(qm) - b^2/(4m^2)} = m \{C_1 + [-b/(qm) - b^2/(4m^2)]^{1/2} C_1^{-1/2} + \dots$$

$$\text{Where } C_1 = [-1/(baq)^2 + 1] \quad ((8b))$$

Thus, the first term of $e = E - m = \sqrt{C_1 - 1}m$ and the second is $-b/(q)$ followed by $O(1/m)$. ((9))

$$\text{Alternatively } (e^2 + 2em) = -m^2/(baq)^2 \quad ((9a))$$

Using ((8b)) and ((6)) one finds the first correction to be:

$$\left\{ -1/(aq) * 1 / [.5 \pm \sqrt{.25 + 1/q^2 a^2}] \right\} \quad ((9b))$$

Relativistic Corrections to the Nonrelativistic Ground State

In (2) and (3) a method was implemented for trying to find relativistic corrections by using the original relativistic equation. We apply such a method. Then:

$$-2mV W(x) - V^2 W(x) = -d/dx d/dx W(x) \quad \text{from above } ((10))$$

$W(x) = \exp(-\sqrt{-E^2 + m^2}) G(x)$ so the leading terms have m as a coefficient. Thus:

$$-2mV G = 2 \sqrt{-E^2 + m^2} d/dx G \quad ((11))$$

This equation replaces the Schrodinger equation, but there is a question as to its physical interpretation. This is considered in the last section. We find that although this is not the Schrodinger equation, it gives a wavefunction whose kinetic energy is the nonrelativistic result with a small correction term of order $1/2m$ which may be dropped compared to the other terms.

((11)) should allow for the calculation of the m order term of e from ((9))

$$\sqrt{-EE + mm} = \sqrt{-e^2 - 2em} = m \sqrt{-A^2 - 2A} \quad \text{where } e = E - m = Am \text{ to first order}$$

$$-VG = \sqrt{-A^2 - 2A} d/dx G \quad ((12))$$

G can be solved by inspection as $G = (1 - q \exp(-ax))^b$ so:

$$-1 = \sqrt{-A^2 - 2A} qab$$

This allows one to obtain A , which gives $e = Am$, the first order energy term which matches ((9a))

To obtain the next term, consider:

$$e^*e \text{ approx} = (Am+c)(Am+c) = A^*Am^*m + 2Ac_m + \dots$$

$$\text{sqrt}(e^*e + 2em) = \text{sqrt}(m^*m(A^*A+2A) + m^2c(A+1)+\dots)$$

$$= m \text{ sqrt}(A^*A+2A) \{1 + c(A+1)/ [m(A^*A+2A)] + \dots\}$$

The constant term is: $c(A+1)/ [\text{sqrt}(A)\text{sqrt}(A+2)]$. Next:

$$V^*V G = -2 c(A+1)/ [\text{sqrt}(A)\text{sqrt}(A+2)] d/dx G - d/dx d/dx G \quad ((13))$$

The problem with ((13)) is it would force other corrections to e to be 0 which they are not. Thus, one may try to solve using:

$$\{\text{sqrt}(e^*e+2m) - m \text{ sqrt}(A^*A+2A)\} d/dx G \text{ in } ((13)) \text{ or}$$

$$-V^*V G = -2 \{\text{sqrt}(e^*e+2m) - m \text{ sqrt}(A^*A+2A)\} d/dx G - d/dx d/dx G \quad ((13))$$

One may solve ((13)) using $G=(1-q\exp(-ax))^b$ and obtain a value for the quantity in {} as one knows A. This may then be expanded in powers of m and one may obtain c. The result should be the same as that from ((9)).

Thus, one is really solving the Klein-Gordon equation in two stages by picking out and equating terms proportional to m and then equating the remaining items. The same wavefunction G applies to both equations although one separates $-d/dx d/dx W$ into two pieces, one proportional to m and the remaining items.

Is One Dealing with the Schrodinger Equation in the Nonrelativistic Case?

Normally, one assumes $e \ll m$ and obtains the Schrodinger equation from either the Klein-Gordon or Dirac equations. In the problem above, $e=Am$ to first order. If $A \ll 1$ then $e \ll m$ should still be satisfied i.e.:

$$(e+m)(e+m) - m^*m - V^*V - 2mV \text{ approx } 2me = p^*p$$

Here A^*A is considered small compared to A and is dropped. Then, one obtains $e - V^*V - 2mV = p^*p/2m$ which is the classical, nonrelativistic result if one may drop $V^*V/2m$. Consider next:

$$-1/2m d/dx d/dx \{ [\exp(-\text{sqrt}(2Am) x) G] \} = \text{classical kinetic energy } \exp() G$$

Here we use the relativistic wavefunction above, but substitute $\sqrt{-2Am}$ for $\sqrt{-E^*E+m^*m}$.

Classical kinetic energy $\exp() G = -1/2m (-2mE) \exp() G - 1/2m \exp() d/dx d/dx G$

Use ((12))

$KE=E \exp() G - 1/2m \exp() G (-1/2m)\{-baaqV - 2m \sqrt{A} aq V+ b(b-1)aaq VV \}$
((14))

$-1/2m (-baaq) V$ is a lower order term which we drop.

$A=\{ -1/(aq) * 1/ [.5+/- \sqrt{.25 + 1/q^2a^2}] \}$. It seems a and q must be large for A to be small, thus a large a^*q gives the classical assumption.

Next: $b= .5 +/- \sqrt{.25 + 1/q^2a^2}$ from ((6)) or $b=1$ for large q^*q .

Thus:

Kinetic energy = $E - V$ ((15)) which is the classical result. Thus, ((6))

$-2mV G = - 2 \sqrt{-E^*E+m^*m} d/dx G$ is very similar (although not exactly) the Schrodinger equation. It does, however, give a result $W(x)= \exp(-\sqrt{2me}x) G$ which yields almost exactly the nonrelativistic quantum kinetic energy.

Higher Energy Levels for the Schrodinger Like Equation

Equation ((11)) seems to take the place of the Schrodinger equation for the nonrelativistic situation of a Hulthen potential. We have examined the ground state energy, but this leaves higher energy levels. Consider:

$W_n(x)= \exp(-\sqrt{-E^*E+m^*m}) G W_1(x)$ where G is as before. Now E is the energy of an excited state.

Let us assume that $e=A(1/b)m$, where $1/b$ is a coefficient which must be determined. For the ground state $b=1$. Then:

$-VG W_1 = -\sqrt{2A/b} \{ (d/dx G) W_1 + G d/dx W_1 \}$ ((16))

$-V [\sqrt{b}+1 -1] G W_1 = -\sqrt{2A} \{ (d/dx G) W_1 + G d/dx W_1 \}$

Now $-\sqrt{d/dx G} = -VG$ so:

$-V [\sqrt{b}-1] W_1 = -\sqrt{2A} d/dx W_1$ ((17))

Taking the second derivative of this e

$$- \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) [\sqrt{b}-1] W_1 + -V [\sqrt{b}-1] \frac{d}{dx} W_1 = -\sqrt{2A} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1 \quad ((18))$$

Next, let $z = \exp(-ax)$ so $\frac{d}{dx} = -az \frac{d}{dz}$ and $\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} = a^2 z^2 \frac{d}{dz} \frac{d}{dz} + aaz \frac{d}{dz}$.

V is of the form $z/(1-qz)$ and $\frac{d}{dx} V$ proportional to $z^*z/(1-qz)^2$ and has another term proportional to $z/(1-qz)$ so it seems ((18)) may be solved using the Nikiforov-Uvarov method. Thus, higher energy levels of this quasi-Schrodinger equation may yield higher energy levels. Of course, one may solve the original Klein-Gordon equation using this method in the first place and then take the nonrelativistic limit. Nevertheless, this seems like an alternative approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to apply the method of (2),(3) to obtain relativistic corrections to the nonrelativistic ground state energy. The relativistic equation in question is the Klein-Gordon with a scalar Hulthen potential $S \exp(-ax) / (1-q \exp(-ax))$. In particular, we find the first two terms of e where $e+m=E$. Thus, if one were not able to solve the Klein-Gordon equation with the Nikiforov-Uvarov method, and even could not solve the Schrodinger equation, one could obtain the first two terms (or more) of the ground state energy. The first term corresponds to a Schrodinger type value, but the second is a correction. In fact, it seems that one can do more.

We find that the Klein-Gordon equation reduces to an equation ((6)) which is not exactly the Schrodinger equation, but whose solutions give the nonrelativistic kinetic energy (if one drops a $1/2m$ small term). Thus, one does not necessarily have to solve the Schrodinger equation for a nonrelativistic solution. There may be a similar DE which follows from the relativistic equation in a nonrelativistic limit. Such an equation may be solvable analytically.

It is interesting to note, that the leading term of e , where $e+m = E$, is Am . Thus, the energy used in the nonrelativistic situation is not always of order of $1/m$ etc.

References

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